

The first record of *Apochinomma elongatum* Haddad, 2013 from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The ant-like sac spider *Apochinomma elongatum* Haddad, 2013 is known from Botswana, Malawi, and Tanzania. This species was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Apochinomma* Pavesi, 1881 represented by 16 species is recorded from the Afrotropical, Neotropical, and Oriental Regions (World Spider Catalog, 2022), but it remains unclear whether the genus is monophyletic. They belong to the Castianeirinae, a subfamily of the Corinnidae, that are generally regarded as good examples of Batesian mimics of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). Representatives of the genus are particularly good examples of the morphological adaptations to ant mimicry, including their elongated cephalothoraxes, modified abdomens, and long legs to enforce an ant-like appearance (Haddad, 2013).

The Afrotropical species was revised by Haddad (2013) and six species were recognized, of which two species – *A. formicaeforme* Pavesi, 1881 and *A. decepta* Haddad, 2013 – were from South Africa. Since then, one West African species, *A. tuberculata* Haddad, 2013, was transferred to *Aetius* O.P.-Cambridge, 1897 by Caleb and Mathai (2016).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). One of the surveys focused on grassland areas in the Gauteng province (Webb, 2014). Over a period of six years, an *Apochinomma* species was repeatedly sampled and photographed by the third author (PW). The *Apochinomma* species was identified by the second author (CH) as *A. elongatum* Haddad, 2013. A single specimen was also sampled from Ndumo Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal in 2021.

The holotype male of *A. elongatum* was described from Nxai Pan National Park, in Botswana and paratype males from Zomba Plateau in Malawi and Mkomazi Game Reserve, Tanzania. The records of *A. elongatum* from Irene and Ndumo Game Reserve represent the first for South Africa.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Apochinomma elongatum Haddad, 2013

Apochinomma elongate Haddad, 2013: 2522 (m).

Diagnostic characteristics: Male: TL 8.73 (7.40–13.60) mm. In live specimens the body and legs are dark grey with dense layer of short white setae; carapace and abdomen with black mottling on clypeus, in and behind eye region and along lateral margins of carapace; abdomen with dark markings on anterior edge and broad horizontal band posteriorly (Figs 1 & 2). Carapace elongate oval, eye region broad, tapering posteriorly to pedicel, broadest at coxa II–III; raised from eye region, without median depression (Figs 1–3); surface finely granulated, covered in short, straight, white setae (Fig. 7), with sparse white, feathery setae; eyes with anterior eye row narrower than posterior eye row; anterior row slightly procurved, medians larger than laterals; posterior eye row strongly recurved, laterals slightly larger than medians (Fig. 6).

Figures 1–3. *Apochinomma elongatum* male from Irene. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Apochinomma elongatum* male: 4. Habitus dorsal view (alcohol material). 5. Palp embolus tip. 6. Carapace showing eye pattern. 7. Anterior view. 8. Male palp. Photo credits: 4, 5, 8. Charles Haddad. 6–7. Peter Webb.

Abdomen elongate, broadened posteriorly, with distinct median constriction and long pedicel; dorsum densely covered in white, feathery setae. Leg formula 4123; legs with short spines, all segments except tarsi usually covered in white and pale yellow, feathery, and straight setae (Fig. 9). Palp slender, with long needle-like embolus, at least half tegulum length (Figs 5 & 8). Female: unknown.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Known from five scattered localities in Southern and East Africa: previously known from Botswana, Malawi, South Africa, and Tanzania and recorded from South Africa for the first time here.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Irene, Centurion (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23) (NCA 2014/990; 2014/3712; 2015/3303; 2016/5588). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve, Nyamiti Pan (-26.89, 32.31) (NCA 2021/246).

LIFESTYLE

A ground-dwelling species recorded from woodland (Tanzania), grassland (Botswana), and wetland habitats (Malawi). The specimens from South Africa were hand collected from a small patch of grassland near Irene (Fig. 10). Specimens at Irene were sampled on 14 June (2009), 12 and 23 November (2013), 16 November (2014), and 12 September (2015). At Ndumo it was found by hand collecting under logs on 3 December (2019). It is most likely a mimic of large epigeic ponerine ants.

Figure 10. The small pristine grassland area about 10 km from Irene where *Apochinomma elongatum* specimens were sampled. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 9. *Apochinomma elongatum* male. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution in the Afrotropical Region but it is under-sampled in South Africa. It can be considered Least Concern.

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